

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 3(12)

27.03.2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOIIY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

 [@fer_teach_uz](https://t.me/fer_teach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.Yu.Bakirov - ped. f.b. PhD, FarDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.B.Mallabayev - tarix f.n., dotsent. NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

X.K.Boymirzayev - ped. f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

I.U.Kuzikulov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

G.K.Obidova- p.f.b. PhD, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

B.T.Mirzadjanov - tarix f.b. PhD, , NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

M.A.Maxmudov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

B.Ya.Tursunov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b.PhD, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Sh.J.Kholmatov - i.i.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Z.N.Khatamova- t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.M.Umurzakova - t.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

L.P.Mamasaidov - tarix f.b. PhD, NamDU, Namangan, O'zbekiston

HYPERPARATHYROIDISM OF VARIOUS GENESIS IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH SHERESHEVSKY-TURNER SYNDROME: A SERIES OF OBSERVATIONS AND A BRIEF REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Kurbanova Nozima Sabirdjanovna

Scientific adviser, Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology,

Oqboyeva Aziza

Borotov Begzod

Davronov Abdullox

Asrorova Marhabo

Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation. *Hyperparathyroidism is a syndrome characterized by increased concentrations of parathyroid hormone. Etiologically, hyperparathyroidism is divided into primary, which develops as a result of neoplasm of the parathyroid glands, and secondary, which occurs compensatorily, in response to a decrease in calcium levels. Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome may also be accompanied by disorders of mineral metabolism of various origins. The simultaneous presence of hyperparathyroidism and Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome in one patient is of interest from the point of view of the multifactorial effect on bone tissue, however, isolated cases of such a combination are described in the literature. This article describes two patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome and hyperparathyroidism of various origins. Laboratory tests in both cases revealed hyperparathyroidism against the background of normocalcemia and vitamin D deficiency, osteoporosis was also diagnosed, and mass formations of the parathyroid glands were identified. In one case, a series of tests made it possible to diagnose normocalcemic primary hyperparathyroidism, and surgical treatment was performed to achieve remission of the disease. In the second case, compensation for vitamin D deficiency led to normalization of the serum concentration of parathyroid hormone, after which the patient was prescribed antiresorptive therapy. Pathogenetic associations of hyperparathyroidism and Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome require further research, and a group of such patients requires an integrated approach to the diagnosis and treatment of mineral metabolism disorders.*

KEYWORDS: *Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome; primary hyperparathyroidism; secondary hyperparathyroidism; vitamin D.*

ГИПЕРПАРАТРООЗ РАЗЛИЧНОГО ГЕНЕЗА У МОЛОДЫХ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С СИНДРОМОМ ШЕРЕШЕВСКОГО-ТЁРНЕРА: РЯД НАБЛЮДЕНИЙ И КРАТКИЙ ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

Курбанова Нозима Сабирджановна

Научный руководитель, ассистент кафедры эндокринологии,

Окбоева Азиза

Боротов Бегзод

Давронов Абдуллох

Асророва Мархабо

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Аннотация. Гиперпаратиреоз – синдром, характеризующийся повышением концентрации паратгормона. По этиологии гиперпаратиреоз разделяют на первичный, развивающийся вследствие новообразования паращитовидных желез, и вторичный, возникающий компенсаторно, в ответ на снижение уровня кальция. Синдром Шерешевского-Тёрнера может также сопровождаться нарушениями минерального обмена различного генеза. Одновременное наличие гиперпаратиреоза и синдрома Шерешевского-Тёрнера у одного пациента представляет интерес с точки зрения многофакторного воздействия на костную ткань, однако в литературе описаны единичные случаи такого сочетания. В статье описаны два пациента с синдромом Шерешевского-Тёрнера и гиперпаратиреозом различного генеза. Лабораторные исследования в обоих случаях выявили гиперпаратиреоз на фоне нормокальциемии и дефицита витамина D, также диагностирован остеопороз, выявлены массивные образования паращитовидных желез. В одном случае серия исследований позволила диагностировать нормокальциемический первичный гиперпаратиреоз и было проведено хирургическое лечение для достижения ремиссии заболевания. Во втором случае компенсация дефицита витамина D привела к нормализации сывороточной концентрации паратгормона, после чего больному была назначена антирезорбтивная терапия. Патогенетические ассоциации гиперпаратиреоза и синдрома Шерешевского-Тёрнера требуют дальнейшего изучения, а группа таких больных требует комплексного подхода к диагностике и лечению нарушений минерального обмена.

Ключевые слова: синдром Шерешевского-Тёрнера; первичный гиперпаратиреоз; вторичный гиперпаратиреоз; Витамин D.

Introduction. Hyperparathyroidism (HPT) is a clinical and laboratory syndrome characterized by an increase in the serum concentration of parathyroid hormone (PTH) [1]. Etiologically, HPT can be divided into primary (PHPT), caused by the primary pathology of the parathyroid glands (PTG) - adenoma/hyperplasia/carcinoma, and secondary (SHPT), representing compensatory hyperfunction of the glands against the background of other disorders of mineral metabolism. SHPT can be caused by a decrease in the filtration function of the kidneys, vitamin D deficiency or disorders of its metabolism, malabsorption (for example, in celiac disease, chronic pancreatitis, inflammatory bowel diseases, etc.), liver failure and a number of other conditions [2]. PHPT is the third most common endocrine disease: with active screening, its incidence in the general population ranges from 0.1 (USA) to 0.43% (Sweden). The overall prevalence of PHPT has been described as 27–30 cases per 100,000 patient-years [3]. It is important to note that with the active detection of PHPT, the clinical structure of the disease is dominated by low-symptomatic and normocalcemic forms, requiring differential diagnosis with SHPT [4–5]. It is believed that PHPT is most common in postmenopausal women [6], although this pattern is not observed in all populations [7]. A number of studies have even suggested the presence of a pathogenetic relationship between the onset of menopause and the development of PHPT [8], but today this remains only a hypothesis. Nevertheless, studying the pathology of the parathyroid gland in patients with hypogonadism is of particular interest. This article discusses two cases of HPT in patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome (STS), which required careful differential diagnosis.

Case description 1. For the first time, patient A. contacted the Federal State Budgetary Institution “National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology” of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan in April 2019 at the age of 31 with complaints of aching bones. From the anamnesis it was known that in 2000 (at the age of 13) she was diagnosed with STS (46Xi/45X0) with turneroid gonadal dysgenesis. For primary hypergonadotropic hypogonadism, she received hormone replacement therapy for a long time: first with ethinyl estradiol 50 mcg/day, then with estradiol valerate 2 mg and medroxyprogesterone acetate 10 mg in a cyclic regimen. The patient also took levothyroxine sodium due to primary hypothyroidism that developed as part of STS. In 2010, according to the words, for the first time an increase in the concentration of serum calcium and intact parathyroid hormone (iPTH) was noted; a year later, during an ultrasound, a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 14x8 mm was

visualized. In 2014, X-ray densitometry (DEXA) was performed, and a decrease in bone mineral density (BMD) was noted below the expected age values: to -2.4 SD in the lumbar spine as a whole and to -2.6 SD in L1 according to the Z-criterion. Due to vitamin D deficiency, the patient received therapy with colecalciferol. The results of laboratory studies for that period are presented.

Results of physical, laboratory and instrumental studies During the examination at the time of the first hospitalization at the Federal State Budgetary Institution "National Medical Research Center of Endocrinology" of the Ministry of Health of Russia, the classical "stigmas" of STS were not noted - the shape of the upper and lower extremities, posture without features, no pterygoid folds of the neck, height 150 cm. Appealed We noticed a lack of body weight - BMI 17.3 kg/m² (Fig. 1 A, B). According to laboratory examination, against the background of normocalcemia, normophosphatemia, normocalciuria and vitamin D deficiency, an increase in iPTH concentration was noted (Table 1). Renal filtration function was preserved—eGFR according to CKD-EPI was 101 ml/min/1.73 m². At the same time, during an ultrasound, the formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 9x6x7 mm was confirmed. According to the DEXA results, in the radius the decrease in BMD was -2.9 SD, in the proximal femur -1.3 SD, in the lumbar spine -1.6 SD according to the Z-criterion. To determine the etiology of HPT, a short test with alfacalcidol (1 mcg/day for three days) was carried out in the department, against which a decrease in the serum concentration of iPTH to 128.5 pg/ml was noted while normocalcemia was maintained (Table 1). The condition was regarded as SHPT, the patient was discharged with recommendations to take alfacalcidol 0.25 mcg/day and colecalciferol at a prophylactic dose (1000 IU/day). According to her, the patient took the prescribed medications regularly. A year later, during another hospitalization at the National Medical Research Center for Endocrinology, an increase in serum PTH concentration was again recorded against the background of normocalcemia and normocalciuria. In addition, there was a negative dynamics of BMD according to DEXA results. Ultrasound also visualized a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland with moderate negative dynamics in size (16x10x11 mm). The dose of alfacalcidol in the hospital was increased to 1 mcg/day, against the background of which a decrease in iPTH levels was again observed while normocalcemia was maintained (Table 1). The patient was discharged with recommendations to continue taking alfacalcidol at a dose of 1.5 mcg/day, against which clinically significant changes in parameters were not achieved. When examined in 2021, despite long-term intake of colecalciferol 2000 IU/day and

alfacalcidol 1.5 mcg/day, laboratory indicators of mineral metabolism remained unchanged (Table 1). In this regard, it was decided to replace alfacalcidol with calcitriol 1 mcg/day for 1 month. Upon further evaluation of the indicators, normocalcemia, persistently elevated iPTH (130 pg/ml) were noted, and hypercalciuria (11 mmol/day) developed for the first time, which made it possible to establish the primary genesis of hyperparathyroidism.

During dynamic screening for complications of hyperparathyroidism, renal filtration function remained satisfactory (eGFR according to EPI 118 ml/min/1.73 m²), multislice computed tomography (MSCT) revealed signs of left-sided nephrolithiasis, and according to esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGDS), erosive esophagitis was diagnosed. According to DEXA, the maximum decrease in BMD reached -2.6 SD according to the Z-score in the radius and femur. Considering the young age of the patient, an examination was carried out to exclude space-occupying formations of the pituitary gland and neuroendocrine tumors of the gastrointestinal tract: no clinical signs of multiple endocrine neoplasia syndrome type 1 were found. During topical diagnostics (ultrasound, scintigraphy with single-photon emission computed tomography, fine-needle aspiration biopsy with PTH washout), a formation of the left lower parathyroid gland measuring 16x12x9 mm was verified). Treatment In April 2022, a left selective parathyroidectomy (SPT) was performed. Outcome and results of follow-up In the early postoperative period, normalization of iPTH (20 pg/ml) was achieved with transient hypocalcemia (Ca total 2.03 mmol/l). According to histological examination, PTG adenoma was verified. In the postoperative period, the patient received alfacalcidol for a month; when stable normocalcemia was achieved, therapy was continued only with colecalciferol. Dynamic monitoring of the patient is currently ongoing.

Case description2. Patient D., 47 years old, was admitted to the department of pathology of the parathyroid glands and disorders of mineral metabolism in 2018 with complaints of severe weakness, drowsiness, fatigue, and a feeling of a lump in the throat when swallowing. Since 1986 (from the age of 15), she was observed by an endocrinologist for STS, but did not receive hormone replacement therapy. In 2011, she suffered a fracture of the neck of the left humerus in a fall from her own height, after which DEXA was performed, the results of which revealed osteoporosis (medical documentation data were not provided).

CONCLUSION. A decrease in bone mineral density in patients with Shereshevsky-Turner syndrome is a consequence of a number of pathophysiological mechanisms, which are based on hypogonadism and disorders

of mineral metabolism. Among the latter, in particular, vitamin D deficiency/insufficiency and subsequent SHPT, as well as PHPT, can be observed. This determines the need for an integrated approach in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with STS. Of particular interest for further study are the pathogenetic associations between PHPT and STS.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбиллов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.
2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191.
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондилов Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исматова ИФ, Бердиеров ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабет COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*.2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.

12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ. Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A Clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin D deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferentsionaldiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):135-138.
20. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
21. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of covid-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2
22. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):381-386.
23. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*. 2023;4(1):131-133.
24. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
25. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovna XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):341-345.

26. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health*. 2022;8:67-72.
27. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
28. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
29. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journal of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR)*. 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
30. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX*. Published online 2020:460-461.
31. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):259-264.
32. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):121-123.
33. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfieva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):107-117.
34. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
35. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. Herpetic meningitis. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
36. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
37. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
38. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
39. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
40. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o'zgarishlar. *so'ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
41. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.

42. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
43. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
44. Daminov AT, Sa'dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
45. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O'g'li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.
46. Ulugbekovna NP, Bakhtiyorovna RI, Almosovich RA, Takhirovich DA. Thyroid Diseases during Pregnancy and their Impact on Maternal and Fetal Outcomes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):188-190.
47. Nilufar R, Adkhamjon K. TO The development of cardiovascular diseases effects of environmental factors. *Fan, ta'lim, madaniyat va innovatsiya jurnali | Journal of science, education, culture and innovation*. 2022;1(4):100-101.
48. Xoldorov X, Omonov F, Jumayev I, Daminov AT. Type 1 diabetes as a risk factor for bone health in childhood. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):131-135.
49. Daminov AT, Xurramova S, Islomov A, Ulashev M, Ikramov R, Mirzakhakimov P. Type 2 diabetes and bone mineral density in postmenopausal women. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(11).
50. Berkinov A, Safarov F, Tursunova S, Daminov AT. Vitamin D status in senior residents of samarkand region. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2023;2(8):136-140.
51. Taxirovich DA, N SY, I IM, Z SM. Vitamin-D yetishmovchiligining qandli diabet 1-tip rivojlanishiga ta'siri. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:74-77.

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 03. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 03. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg‘ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMlarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 03. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 03. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 03. 2024

Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

Е-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 03. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 03. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 03. | 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyliги uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.